

Ultrasonic study of molecular interactions and determination of acoustical parameters of transition and lanthanide metal myristates in non-aqueous medium

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Abstract : Ultrasonic velocity measurements on transition and lanthanide metal myristates have been carried out in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v) in order to determine the critical micellar concentration, soap-solvent interactions and various acoustic and thermodynamic parameters. The results have been discussed in terms of different theories of ultrasonic wave propagation and Jacobson's model has also been used to calculate adiabatic and molar compressibilities intermolecular free length, solvation number, relative association, relaxation strength and molar sound velocity. The results of ultrasonic measurements have also been explained in terms of various well known equations.

Keywords : Ultrasonic velocity, acoustical parameters, molecular interaction, adiabatic compressibility, specific acoustic impedance, solvation number.

Introduction

Lanthanide metal soaps were synthesised for the first time by Misra *et al.*^{1,2} in the early 60s. These soaps are being used as polymer stabilizers, catalysts and in optical polymer fibers^{3,4}. The properties and applications of metallic soap depends on the length of the fatty acid chain and on the associated metal cations, their physical state, stability, chemical reactivity and solubility in polar as well as in non-polar solvents. Soaps are invariably termed as association colloids. The association of small molecules or ions in to micelles seem to be more characteristic than, the electrolytic character which plays a great role in soap solutions. Soaps play a definite role in industries such as, textiles, metal cleaning, electroplating cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, fire fighting, paints, varnishes, food and agricultural industries. While stupendous developments have taken place in the study of alkali and alkaline-earths metal soaps but the investigations on transition and lanthanide metal soaps have lagged behind. The survey of literature is indicative of the fact that the manganese, copper, zinc,

cerium, praseodymium and neodymium myristates have not yet been studies systematically. These soaps have attracted the attention of industries and are finding applications in many fields. The studies on the nature and structure of these soaps are of paramount importance for their uses in various industries and for explaining their characteristics under different conditions.

Experimental

AR grade benzene, methanol, ethanol, myristic acid, and various transition and lanthanide metals salts were used for present investigations. The transition and lanthanide metal myristates were prepared by the direct metathesis of potassium myristates with a slight stoichiometric excess of aqueous solution of corresponding metal acetate at 50–60 °C under vigorous stirring. The precipitate were filtered off and washed with doubly distilled water and acetone before drying. The purity of these soaps was checked by carbon and hydrogen analysis and the results were found in fair agreement with theoretically calculated values. The ultrasonic velocity of the solutions of transition

and lanthanide metal myristates were recorded on a multi-frequency ultrasonic interferometer "Model MX-3" Mittal Enterprises, at different temperatures using a crystal of frequency 1 MHz. The uncertainty of velocity measurements was 0.2%. The densities were determined with the help of specific gravity bottle. All the measurements were made at 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C.

The adiabatic β and molar compressibility, W have been calculated by the following relationships.

$$\beta = \rho^{-1} v^{-2} \quad (1)$$

$$W = \bar{M}/\rho (\beta)^{-1/7} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density and v is the ultrasonic velocity of solution, $\bar{M} = (n_o M + n M_o)/n_o + n$, where $n M$, and $n_o M_o$ are number of moles and molecular weight of solute and solvent, respectively and \bar{M} stands for effective molecular weight.

The intermolecular free length⁷ L_f and specific acoustic impedance⁸, Z , i.e. unit area acoustic impedance of a sound medium in given surface have been evaluated using the relationships.

$$L_f = K\sqrt{\beta} \quad (3)$$

$$Z = \rho v \quad (4)$$

where K is Jacobson's constant.

The apparent molar compressibility, ϕ_k in solution were calculated from the compressibility and density data by using the relationship :

$$\phi_k = \frac{1000}{C\rho_o} (\rho_o - \beta_o\rho) + \frac{\beta_o M}{\rho_o} \quad (5)$$

The primary solvation number, S_n was calculated by the modified expansion of Pasynsky⁹ while the molar sound velocity¹⁰, R was determined by the equations :

$$S_n = \frac{n_o}{n} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{v}\beta}{n_o\bar{v}_o\beta} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$R = \frac{\bar{M}}{\rho} - v^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

where \bar{v} is the molar volume of solution containing n moles of solute and \bar{v}_o is the molar volume of

solvent mixture.

The relative association¹¹, R_A , available volume¹², V_a and relaxation strength, r were calculated by the relationships :

$$R_A = (\rho/\rho_o) (v_o/v)^{1/3} \quad (8)$$

$$V_a = \bar{V} (1 - v/v_o) \quad (9)$$

$$r = 1 - (v/v_\alpha)^2 \quad (10)$$

where v_α is equivalent to 1600 m s⁻¹.

Results and discussion

The trends of variation of the various acoustical parameters with change in concentration, at different temperatures (30, 35, 40 and 45 °C) for transition and lanthanide metal myristates have been studied. The ultrasonic velocity for the solution of transition and lanthanide metal myristates in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v) increases with increasing concentration and size of metal cations. For any homogeneous dissipative liquid system, the velocity, v of compressional acoustic wave is related to the density, ρ and adiabatic compressibility, β by the relationship :

$$v = (\rho\beta)^{-1/2} \quad (11)$$

The variation of velocity with concentration depends upon the concentration derivatives of density and compressibility and may be expressed in this manner :

$$\frac{dv}{dC} = -\frac{v}{2} \left[\frac{1}{\rho} \cdot \frac{d\rho}{dC} + \frac{1}{\beta} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{dC} \right] \quad (12)$$

The results (Table 1) indicate, that the density increases where as the adiabatic compressibility decreases with increasing soap concentration. Therefore, the concentration derivative of density, $(d\rho/dC)$, is positive while the concentration derivative of compressibility, $(d\beta/dC)$, is negative. Since the quantity $1/\beta(d\beta/dC)$ predominates over $1/\rho(d\rho/dC)$, for these soap solution, the concentration derivative of velocity, (dv/dC) , will be positive and so the velocity increases with increasing concentration of transition and lanthanide metal myristates. These results are in agreement with the results of several workers reported for electrolytic solutions^{13,14}.

The ultrasonic velocity increases with the increase in concentration of transition and lanthanide metal

Table 1. Ultrasonic velocity and compressibility of manganese myristate in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v) at 30 ± 0.05 °C

Sl. no.	Concentration $C \times 10^3$ (g.mol L ⁻¹)	Density ρ (g.ml ⁻¹)	Velocity $v \times 10^{-5}$ (cm/s)	Adiabatic compressibility $\beta \times 10^{11}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	Molar compressibility $W \times 10^{-2}$ [cm ³ /mol]. [dyne/cm ²] ^{-1/7}	Apparent molar compressibility $t - (\phi_k) \times 10^6$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	Relaxation strength (r)
1.	2.0	0.8592	1.119	9.291	17.93	1.2555	0.5109
2.	2.4	0.8601	1.124	9.203	18.01	1.5046	0.5065
3.	3.0	0.8614	1.130	9.092	18.11	1.6698	0.5012
4.	3.7	0.8629	1.139	8.933	18.24	1.8860	0.4932
5.	4.9	0.8646	1.143	8.853	18.43	1.6368	0.4892
6.	5.5	0.8653	1.144	8.830	18.52	1.5142	0.4888
7.	6.2	0.8661	1.146	8.792	18.63	1.4217	0.4870
8.	7.1	0.8672	1.148	8.750	18.75	1.3193	0.4852
9.	7.6	0.8678	1.149	8.729	18.84	1.2691	0.4843
10.	3.3	0.8685	1.151	8.691	18.95	1.2194	0.4825
11.	9.0	0.8694	1.153	8.652	19.08	1.1808	0.4807
12.	10.0	0.8705	1.155	8.611	19.21	1.1161	0.4789

Intermolecular free length, solvation number and other allied parameters of manganese myristate in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v) at 30 ± 0.05 °C

Sl. no.	Concentration $C \times 10^3$ (g.mol L ⁻¹)	Intermolecular free length L_f (Å)	Specific acoustic impedance $Z \times 10^{-5}$	Solvation number (S_n)	Molar sound velocity (R) [cm ³ /mol]. [cm/cm ²] ^{1/3}	Available volume (V_a)	Relative association (R_A)
1.	2.0	0.6188	0.9614	203.38	3183	19.865	0.9984
2.	2.4	0.6159	0.9668	243.74	3197	19.711	0.9980
3.	3.0	0.6121	0.9734	270.50	3215	19.541	0.9977
4.	3.7	0.6058	0.9829	305.52	3238	19.256	0.9968
5.	4.9	0.6040	0.9883	265.15	3271	19.259	0.9976
6.	5.5	0.6033	0.9899	245.29	3287	19.305	0.9981
7.	6.2	0.6019	0.9925	230.31	3307	19.323	0.9964
8.	7.1	0.6005	0.9955	213.59	3330	19.366	0.9991
9.	7.6	0.5998	0.9972	205.59	3343	19.394	0.9995
10.	8.3	0.5985	0.9997	197.54	3363	19.410	0.9998
11.	9.0	0.5972	1.0024	191.29	3386	19.421	1.0002
12.	10.0	0.5957	1.0055	180.80	3409	19.475	1.0009

myristates in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v). The intermolecular free length, which is expected to decrease as a results of mixing of the two components¹⁵, decreases with the increase in concentration of soap. A rise in temperature generally increases the internal energy of the system by distorting the local structure, resulting in an increase in the intermolecular free length and subsequently decreasing the ultrasonic velocity. In the present study, the elevation of

temperature from 30 to 45 °C shows the same trend.

The variation in ultrasonic velocity v with concentration of the soap solution, C follow the relationship.

$$v = v_0 + GC \quad (13)$$

where v and v_0 are the ultrasonic velocity in the solution and solvent mixture, respectively and G is Garnsey's constant¹⁶. The plots of ultrasonic velo-

city, v , against soap concentration, C , are characterized by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the critical concentration for micelles formation (Table 2). The results show that the increase in temperature and decrease of the size of metal ions results in the increase of CMC. These plots (Fig. 1) have been ex-

trapolated to zero soap concentration and the extrapolated values of velocity, v_0 are in agreement with the experimental values of velocity of the solvent mixture, indicating that the molecules of transition and lanthanide metal soaps do not aggregate to an appreciable extents below the CMC. The values of Garnsey's constant, G for transition and rare earth

Table 2. Values of critical micellar concentration (CMC) and Garnsey's constant for transition and lanthanide metal myristates in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v)

Sl. no.	Name of the Soap	CMC $\times 10^3$ (g.mole L ⁻¹)				Garnsey's constant (G) 10^{-6}			
		30 °C	35 °C	40 °C	45 °C	30 °C	35 °C	40 °C	45 °C
1.	Manganese myristate	3.85	4.10	4.25	4.45	2.33	2.17	2.00	1.86
2.	Copper myristate	3.90	4.15	4.30	4.50	2.50	2.33	2.17	2.00
3.	Zinc myristate	4.05	4.25	4.45	4.60	2.75	2.55	2.40	2.25
4.	Cerium myristate	4.20	4.25	4.55	4.75	3.33	3.00	2.75	2.50
5.	Praseodymium myristate	5.05	5.20	5.35	5.50	3.86	3.55	3.29	3.00
6.	Neodymium myristate	5.15	5.30	5.50	5.07	4.75	4.50	4.25	4.00

Fig. 1. Ultrasonic velocity vs concentration of cerium myristate in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v).

metals myristates have been calculated from the slope of the linear portion of the plots (below the CMC) of v vs C and are recorded in Table 2. The values of Garnsey's constant decrease with the decrease in size of metal ions. However, these values increase with decreasing temperature. The comparison of the results showed that the values of ultrasonic velocity and Garnsey's constant for lanthanide metals (Ce, Pr and Nd) myristates in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v) were higher than values for transition metal (Mn, Cu and Zn) myristates.

The acoustic data mentioned in this paper has been analyzed in the light of Jacobson's model¹⁷ of the intermolecular free length in liquid. According to the Jacobson's model, the ultrasonic waves are incident on the liquid molecules, the molecules of the liquid get perturbed, and since the medium has some elasticity, the perturbed molecules regain their equilibrium positions. Writing E for bulk modulus of elasticity, the velocity of sound in the medium is given by :

$$v = \sqrt{E/\rho}$$

$$E = v^2 \rho \quad (14)$$

Writing the reciprocal of elasticity as β the compressibility of the liquid we get.

$$\beta = 1/v^2 \rho$$

The nature of adiabatic compressibility variation is mostly found to be reverse to that of ultrasonic velocity¹⁴, this is also evident in the present study. The adiabatic compressibility of transition and lanthanide metal myristates decreases with increase in soap concentration. An increase in concentration of electrolytes in solutions generally lowers the compressibility,

due to greater interaction between the ions, increasing the internal pressure. However the adiabatic compressibility increases with the rise in temperature. The comparison of the results showed that the adiabatic compressibility of transition metal myristates was greater than adiabatic compressibility of lanthanide metal myristates.

The decrease in adiabatic compressibility after critical micellar concentration may be due to the closed packing of ionic head group in the micelles, resulting in an increase in ionic repulsion and finally internal pressure.

The results of adiabatic compressibility, β of the solution of transition and lanthanide metal myristate soaps can be explained, in the light of Bachem's¹⁸ relationship.

$$\beta = \beta^0 + AC + BC^{3/2} \quad (15)$$

where A and B are constants, C is the molar concentration of soap solutions. The plots of $(\beta - \beta^0)/C$ vs \sqrt{C} show a break at the critical micellar concentration. The values of CMC obtained from these plots are in agreement with the CMC determined from other physical properties. The values of constants A and B have been obtained from the intercept and slope of the plots of $(\beta - \beta^0)/C$ vs \sqrt{C} . The values of constants A and B (Table 3) increase with the increase in temperature. However the values of constant A decrease with the increase in size of metal cations. A perusal of the data collected in Table 3 indicates that the values of the constants A and B for lanthanide metal soaps are higher than the values for transition metal soaps. The values of constants A and B obtained from Bachem's relationship for transition and

Table 3. Values of constants A and B obtained from (Bachem's relationship) the plots of $(\beta - \beta_0)/C$ vs \sqrt{C}

Sl. no.	Name of the Soap	$-A \times 10^9$				$B \times 10^8$			
		30 °C	35 °C	40 °C	45 °C	30 °C	35 °C	40 °C	45 °C
1.	Manganese myristate	0.44	0.39	0.33	0.27	3.25	3.50	3.75	4.00
2.	Copper myristate	0.65	0.60	0.54	0.48	2.75	3.00	3.25	3.50
3.	Zinc myristate	0.69	0.65	0.61	0.57	2.67	3.00	3.33	3.67
4.	Cerium myristate	0.31	0.28	0.25	0.21	4.00	4.20	4.40	4.60
5.	Praseodymium myristate	0.39	0.35	0.31	0.27	3.80	4.00	4.20	4.50
6.	Neodymium myristate	0.47	0.43	0.39	0.34	3.60	3.80	4.00	4.35

lanthanide metal myristates are consistent with the results of the other workers¹⁹.

The value of molar compressibility, W , of these metal soaps in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v) increase with the increases in soap concentration and size of metal cations. However, the increase in temperature results in the decrease of molar compressibility. The plots of the molar compressibility, W , vs soap concentration C show a point of inflection at CMC. The comparison of the results indicated that the values of molar compressibility for lanthanide metal soap were higher than the values for transition metal soaps.

Apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) values vary linearly with \sqrt{C} below the CMC for transition and lanthanide metal myristates obeying Gucker's²⁰ limiting law,

$$\phi_k = \phi_k^0 + S_k \sqrt{C} \quad (16)$$

The intercepts (ϕ_k^0) and slopes (S_k) of the plots ϕ_k vs \sqrt{C} below the critical micellar concentration are listed in Table 4. These plots are also characterized by a break at the CMC. The positive values of S_k signifies a considerable soap-solvent interactions below the CMC. It is apparent that the values of $-\phi_k$ decrease sharply upto the CMC and again it increases with square root of soap concentration. The decreases in the values of ϕ_k may be attributed to the fact that the soap molecules in dilute solution are considerably ionized into metal cations and fatty acid anions. These ions surrounded by a thin film of solvent molecules, firmly bound and oriented towards the ions. The orientation of molecules around the ions is attributed to the influence of the electrostatic field of the ions and

thus the internal pressure increases, which reduces the compressibility of the solution²¹. The increase in the values of ϕ_k^0 in the post micellization region indicates the incompressible nature of the concentrated soap solution. The values of limiting apparent molar compressibility ϕ_k^0 and constant S_k (Table 4) increase with the increase in temperature and size of metal cations. The comparison of the results showed that the values of ϕ_k^0 and S_k (Table 4) for lanthanide metal myristates were higher than the value for transition metal myristates.

The values of intermolecular free length⁷, L_f and specific acoustic impedance⁸, Z for transition and lanthanide metal myristates in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture at different temperatures have been calculated. The decrease in the values of intermolecular free length, L_f and increase in the values of specific acoustic impedance, Z with increase in soap concentration can be explained on the basis of hydrophobic interaction between soap and solvent molecules, which increases the intermolecular distance, leaving relatively wider gap between these molecules and thus becoming the main cause of impediment to the propagation of ultrasound waves and ultimately affects structural arrangements. The L_f decrease with the increase in size of metal cations. However, these values increase with increasing temperature. The specific acoustic impedance, a product of the density of the solution and the velocity, has shown the reverse trend to that of intermolecular free length. Thus the fact that increase of velocity, decrease of adiabatic compressibility, decrease of intermolecular free length and increase of specific acoustic impedance with increase in molar concentration is an indicative of the increase

Table 4. Value of limiting apparent molar compressibility ϕ_k^0 and constant S_k obtained from the plots of ϕ_k^0 vs \sqrt{C}

Sl. no.	Name of the Soap	$\phi_k^0 \times 10^6$				$S_k \times 10^4$			
		30 °C	35 °C	40 °C	45 °C	30 °C	35 °C	40 °C	45 °C
1.	Manganese myristate	0.71	0.67	0.63	0.59	3.86	4.14	4.33	4.50
2.	Copper myristate	0.70	0.67	0.64	0.60	4.00	4.25	4.44	4.67
3.	Zinc myristate	0.68	0.65	0.61	0.57	4.25	4.44	4.67	4.86
4.	Cerium myristate	0.62	0.59	0.56	0.53	5.33	5.50	5.86	6.17
5.	Praseodymium myristate	0.60	0.58	0.55	0.52	5.44	5.67	6.00	6.33
6.	Neodymium myristate	0.58	0.55	0.52	0.49	5.75	6.14	6.50	6.86

in intermolecular forces with the addition of soap forming aggregates of solvent molecules around solute ions²¹, supports the strong solute-solvent interactions due to which structural arrangement is affected¹⁵.

The plots of intermolecular free length, L_f vs concentration, C and specific acoustic impedance, Z , vs concentration, C show a break at the CMC and extrapolation of these plots gives the values of pure solvent mixture, indicating that the molecules of transition and lanthanide metal myristates do not aggregate to an appreciable extent below the CMC. The values of L_f for transition metal soaps are higher than lanthanide metal myristates. However the values of specific acoustic impedance have shown the reverse trend.

The values of relaxation strength²², r (Table 1) decrease with the increase in soap concentration and size of the metal cations. These values increase with the rise in temperature. The plots of relaxation strength, r vs concentration, C are characterized by a break at the CMC. The decreasing trend of r with concentration again supports the solute-solvent interactions. The comparison of the results indicated that the values of relaxation strength, r for transition metal soap were higher than the values for lanthanide metal soaps.

The molar sound velocity¹⁰, R increases (Table 1) with the increase in soap concentration and size of metal ions. A rise in temperature increases the molar volume, probably due to decrease in density of these solutions. The molar sound velocity is however, independent of temperature. These results concluded that the molar sound velocity of lanthanide metal myristates were higher than the molar sound velocity of transition metal myristates.

The values of available volume¹², V_a decrease (Table 1) with the increase in soap concentration and size of metal cations. However, the increase in temperature results in the increase of available volume. The plots of available volume vs concentration are also characterized by a break at the CMC. The comparison of the results showed that the values of available volume for transition metal soap were higher than the value of lanthanide metal myristates.

The values of relative association¹¹, R_A and solva-

tion number⁹, S_n for transition and lanthanide metal myristates have been calculated. The values of relative association decreases with the increase in soap concentration. However, these values of relative association, R_A , has been attributed either to the decreased association between soap and mixed organic solvent molecules at higher concentration or increasing solvation of ions. The increase in relative association with increasing temperature is attributed to the decrease in solvation with increase in temperature. The values of relative association for lanthanide metal myristates are higher than the values for transition metal myristates. The values of solvation number correspond to the number of solvent molecules in the primary solvation sheaths of the ions. On account of electrostriction, molecules in the primary solvation sheath will be highly compressed so that these molecules will be less compressible than those in the bulk of the solution when an external pressure is applied. The compressibility of solvent molecules near but not in the primary solvation sheath is the same as that of pure solvent.

The values of solvation number exhibit a marked change above the CMC which may be attributed to greater intake of solvent molecules above the CMC to reduce the repulsive forces action between polar heads of ionic micelles. On comparison it was found that the values of solvation number for lanthanide metal (Ce, Pr and Nd) myristates were higher than the values of solvation number for transition metal (Mn, Cu and Zn) myristates.

Conclusions

Calculated data on ultrasonic velocity indicated that the soaps of transition and lanthanide metal myristates behave as weak electrolyte in 70/30 benzene-methanol mixture (v/v). The results confirm that strong molecular interaction exist in the solution of soaps and these soaps has structure forming tendency in non-aqueous solution state and the soap molecules do not aggregate appreciably below the CMC. The acoustical parameters obtained are in agreement with the results of other workers^{21,23}. These results show that the increase in temperature and decrease of the size of metals ions results in the increase of CMC values.

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